

2: Assessing the regional context of migration in Brazilian Legal Amazonia through spatial regression modeling

Thursday, 2 November 2017

08:45 AM - 09:00 AM

 Cape Town International Convention Centre - Meeting Room 2.63-2.64 (simultaneous interpretation)

Short Abstract

In this paper, we use spatial statistical modeling to examine the context of migration in Brazilian Legal Amazonia by investigating its socioeconomic, demographic, spatial and environmental heterogeneities at the municipal level between 2000 and 2010. We explored the spatial autocorrelation among factors using Global Moran's I Index and Local Indicator of Spatial Autocorrelation. Subsequently, we use spatial modeling techniques to explore the associations between response variables (in-migration and out-migration rates) and selected explanatory variables. Our results indicate that there is significant spatial patterning in in-migration and out-migration rates in Legal Amazonia. The spatial regression models present better estimates of the coefficients by incorporating the spatially lagged autoregressive parameter. These models confirm the multidimensional character of migration in Legal Amazonia, given the observed associations with multiple contextual variables at the municipal level. Finally, we explore in some detail the major implications of this contextual assessment for public policies in Legal Amazonia.

Authors

Douglas dos Reis

UFVJM

Susana Beatriz Adamo

CIESIN-Columbia University

Everton Lima

Centro de Desenvolvimento e Planejamento Regional (CEDEPLAR)

Diego Macedo

Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (UFMG)

Alexander De Sherbinin

Columbia University

Paola Kim-Blanco

Columbia University

 Extended Abstract -

[Assessing the regional context of migration in Brazilian Legal Amazonia through spatial regression modeling.docx](#)

View Related Items

Session: Spatial methods in demography

Theme: Spatial Demography

Assessing the regional context of migration in Brazilian Legal Amazonia through spatial regression modeling

Douglas Sathler (FIH-CeGEO-UFVJM/Brazil); Susana Adamo (CIESIN-Columbia University/US); Everton E. C. Lima (Unicamp/Brazil); Diego Rodrigues Macedo (IGC-UFMG/Brazil); Alex de Sherbinin (CIESIN-Columbia University/US); Paola Kim-Blanco (CIESIN-Columbia University/US)

Introduction

The Brazilian Legal Amazonia contains the most active rainforest frontier in the world, and its socioeconomic, demographic and spatial dynamism has been a topic of interest for academics and policy makers for decades (Schmink and Wood, 1984; 1992; Browder and Godfrey, 1997; Becker, 2005; Fearnside, 2008; Sathler, 2009; Guedes *et al.*, 2012). In Legal Amazonia, the regional migratory history has been strongly associated with deep economic changes. In the 1970s, infrastructure expansion (roads, ports and hydroelectric plants) and the emergence of new economic actors (mining, industry, ranching and soybean producers) triggered intense migration from other parts of Brazil toward the Amazonian frontier (Almeida *et al.*, 1995; Fearnside and Graça, 2009; Ebanyat *et al.*, 2010). Since the 1980s, intraregional migration has been predominant and the evolution of the rainforest frontier was mainly shaped by economic actors already established in the region (Becker, 2005; MMA, 2008). In addition, the most recent Brazilian census (IBGE, 2000; 2010) demonstrate that recent economic changes have enormously increased Amazonian territorial disparities (Lira *et al.*, 2009; Prates and Bacha, 2011), unequally impacting regional development, and featuring increased intraregional migration (Cunha, 2011). Therefore, it is relevant to further investigate this demographic component, specifically along the Amazonian rainforest frontier.

In this paper, we use spatial statistical modeling to examine the context of migration in Legal Amazonia by investigating its socioeconomic, demographic, spatial and environmental heterogeneities at the municipal level between 2000 and 2010. Initially, we explored and visualized the spatial autocorrelation among factors using Global Moran's *I* Index and Local Indicator of Spatial Autocorrelation (LISA). Subsequently, we use spatial modeling techniques to explore the associations between response variables (in-migration and out-migration) and selected explanatory variables. We focus on the following specific questions: 1) Is there any spatial dependence in the explored variables, and, if so, how should this characteristic be appropriately addressed in the spatial regression models? 2) Which contextual factors significantly explain in-migration and out-migration rates in Legal Amazonia? 3) What are the major implications of this contextual assessment for public policies seeking sustainable development in Legal Amazonia?

Data and Methods

This study investigates the associations between internal migration and contextual socioeconomic, demographic, connectivity, and environmental factors, from 740 municipalities⁴ in Legal Amazonia. In this study, internal migration was operationalized as in-migration and out-migration rates, calculated with data from the latest Brazilian census, in 2010 (IBGE, 2010). In-migrants and out-migrants were identified from a sample of individuals who were 5 years old or older in 2010, and who declared to have resided in a different municipality in 2005 (IBGE, 2010); and subsequently aggregated in a migratory matrix at the municipal level. Internal migration rates were calculated using municipal population at the end of the period (2010). Figure 1 presents the study area and the spatial distribution of the in-migration, out-migration and net migration rates at the municipal level in Legal Amazonia.

Figure 1. Main geographical elements, response variables (in-migration and out-migration rates) and net-migration rates in Legal Amazonia, 2005-2010.

Based on a review of the subject's literature, this study focuses on six main dimensions to potentially explain internal migration in Legal Amazonia: a) demographic, b) economic, c) development, d) inequality, e) connectivity, and f) environment. Thirty-nine initial variables were explored, but only twelve are included in the model due to multi-collinearity and confounding issues. In this study, we included the following variables: total population, urban population growth (2000-2010), % population between 20 to 39 years, variation in Gross Domestic Product (2000-2010), % services GDP, Human Development Index (HDI), variation in HDI (2000-2010), Gini index, distance to the closest major center (km), distance to a paved road (km), % deforested area (2005-2010) and % forested area (2010). These variables express the municipal context at the end of the analyzed period (2010) or the variation between the two last Brazilian censuses (2000-2010) at the municipal level. Data sources include the Brazilian census micro-data (IBGE, 2000; 2010), PNUD indicators (2010), Brazilian 1:250.000 maps (IBGE, 2016) and INPE (2000-2010).

In this study, we investigate our data using the global Moran's I index, including both the response (in-migration and out-migration rates) and the twelve explanatory variables. We also decomposed these estimated global indicators by using the Local Indicator of Spatial Autocorrelation (LISA). Subsequent data

transformation included normalizing all predicting variables, subtracting the corresponding mean and dividing by the standard deviation. Moreover, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) models were run to model linear relationships for both in-and-out migration rates. A series of Moran's I among the models' residuals were also conducted, in order to obtain the intensity and significance of the spatial relationships within the error terms. Spatial patterns were also confirmed through Breusch-Pagan tests, via heteroscedasticity. Once spatial associations were confirmed, Lagrange Multiplier (LM) diagnostics were conducted following Anselin's methodology (Anselin, 2004; 2007). Moreover, we estimated the spatial regression models through the maximum likelihood principle according to the equation 2. These models were built based on the spatial weights matrix W (Ward and Gleditsch, 2008).

Results and preliminary discussion

The observed and expected values of global Moran's I index for both explanatory and response variables demonstrate that urban population growth and distance to the closest major center do not exhibit any significant spatial pattern at the 0.05 level. The percentage of forested area (0.833), distance to a paved road (0.658), HDI (0.575), the percentage of deforested area (0.565) and in-migration rates (0.512) present the highest degree of spatial autocorrelation, while total population (0.077) and variation in GDP (0.198) exhibit the lowest Moran's I scores. Furthermore, LISA analysis demonstrates that in-migration rates exhibit high-high clusters throughout the Northern Rondônia, center Mato Grosso, Southeastern Pará and Northern Amapá, while low-low clusters are observed in the Western Amazonas, Northern Pará and Maranhão. Similarly, out-migration rates exhibit high-high clusters throughout the Southern Rondônia, Northern and Central Mato Grosso and Tocantins, while low-low clusters are predominant in Northern Pará, Northern Maranhão and Amazonas. We also identified a group of high-low municipalities in the Southern Legal Amazonia and some low-high municipalities in the Northern Pará, Amapá and Northern Maranhão.

Table 2 presents the results for in-migration and out-migration modeling using both OLS and SLM models. Our results indicate that there is significant spatial patterning in in-migration and out-migration rates in Legal Amazonia. The spatial regression models present better estimates of the coefficients by incorporating the spatially lagged autoregressive parameter. In the SLM explaining in-migration, the coefficient parameter ($Rho = 0.513$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that the sample data presents a positive and highly significant spatial dependence. Turning to the SLM explaining out-migration rates, the coefficient parameter ($Rho = 0.469$, $p < 0.001$) reveals a positive and highly significant effect. This model also presents a great log likelihood value (-815.63) by improving the OLS model in terms of total fit.

In general, these models confirm the multidimensional character of in-migration and out-migration rates in Legal Amazonia, given the observed associations with multiple contextual variables at the municipal level. The *Demographic* variables are crucial in the spatial regression models. First, the significant negative association with population in both spatial regression models highlights the relevance of less-populated municipalities to assure the intense migration flows between 2005 and 2010 in Legal Amazonia (Cunha, 2011). Even though some large and medium-sized municipalities (in terms of population) in Legal Amazonia present higher migration volume in absolute terms between 2005 and 2010, less-populated municipalities exhibited higher proportional changes in population (IBGE, 2010). In addition, related literature reveals that inter-municipal migration is predominantly an urban phenomenon in Legal Amazonia (Becker, 2005; Monte-Mór, 2013). Our findings do not show any contrary evidence, given the negative association between out-migration rates and urban population growth and the insignificant coefficient in the SLM explaining in-migration rates. Moreover, migration can have a substantial impact on population age structure (McDonald and Temple, 2006; Khoo and McDonald, 2011), especially among. We find that both in-migration and out-migration effects on age structure are relevant, given the significant associations between response variables and the percentage of population between 20 to 39 years.

Table 1. Standardized regression coefficients from the OLS and SLM explaining in-migration and out-migration rates in Legal Amazonia, 2005-2010.

Variables	In-migration		Out-migration	
	OLS	SLM	OLS	SLM
Intercept	0.000 (0.028)	0.020 (0.024)	0.000 (0.029)	-0.009 (0.026)
Demographic				
Population	-0.154*** (0.043)	-0.098** (0.038)	-0.211*** (0.046)	-0.121** (0.041)
Urban Population Growth (2000-2010)	-0.004 (0.028)	0.019 (0.025)	-0.099*** (0.030)	-0.072** (0.027)
% Population with 20 to 39 years	0.205*** (0.036)	0.185*** (0.031)	-0.192*** (0.038)	-0.164*** (0.034)
Economic and Development				
Variation in GDP (2000-2010)	0.171*** (0.031)	0.151*** (0.027)	-0.127*** (0.032)	-0.115*** (0.029)
% Services GDP	-0.182*** (0.032)	-0.112*** (0.028)	-0.189*** (0.034)	-0.093** (0.030)
HDI	0.391*** (0.044)	0.195*** (0.040)	0.523*** (0.047)	0.355*** (0.044)
Variation in HDI (2000-2010)	-0.042 (0.039)	0.005 (0.034)	-0.039 (0.041)	-0.068 (0.037)
Inequality				
Gini	-0.058 (0.034)	-0.040 (0.030)	-0.026 (0.037)	0.013 (0.033)
Connectivity				
Distance to the closest major center	-0.062 (0.046)	-0.080* (0.040)	0.099* (0.049)	0.059 (0.044)
Distance to a paved road	-0.012 (0.031)	-0.011 (0.027)	0.047 (0.033)	0.036 (0.030)
Environment				
% Deforested area (2005-2010)	0.102*** (0.030)	0.047 (0.026)	0.185*** (0.032)	0.129*** (0.029)
% Forested area	0.044 (0.033)	0.045 (0.029)	-0.162*** (0.036)	-0.085** (0.032)
N = 740				
Adj R-squared	0.438***		0.364***	
Rho	0.513***		0.469***	
Log likelihood	-756.07		-815.63	

Standard errors are in parentheses. *** p < 0.001; ** p < 0.01; *p < 0.05.

The economic and development variables also dominated the spatial regression models. The significant association between variation in GDP and both in-migration rates (positive) and out-migration rates (negative) confirm the empirical evidences presented by the most prominent literature on economic drivers of migration (Massey *et al.*, 1993). Furthermore, most of the assessed municipalities with a high percentage of services in their GDP composition generally have low levels of investments in the agricultural and industrial sectors, presenting an undiversified and stagnated economy (IBGE 2000; 2010; Sathler *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, the negative association between the percentage of services GDP and both response variables suggests that in-migration and out-migration rates are lower among the most stagnated municipalities. Moreover, the strong positive association between HDI and both in-migration and out-migration rates reflects the high developmental discrepancies among municipalities in Legal Amazonia (Guedes, *et al.* 2012), created by the historically unequal spatial distribution of the private and public investments in the region (MMA, 2008; Fearnside, 2008).

In this analysis, the *distance to the closest major center* is particularly important given the long distances involving many cities and population agglomerations in Legal Amazonia, especially in the regional interior (Sathler *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, although the spatial regression model does not show any evidence of association between in-migration rates and environment variables, previous studies show significant linkages between these variables within rainforest frontier (Wood *et al.*, 1996; Caviglia-Harris *et al.*, 2012). In addition, the positive association with the percentage of deforested areas and the negative association with the percentage of forested area suggest that environmental depletion is shaping out-migration rates in the region.

Finally, interdisciplinary assessments of migration patterns are crucial for public policies seeking sustainable development in Legal Amazonia, given its important interregional migratory history and the continuous intensification on migratory flows. Our findings indicate that policies must decrease the high levels of inequality among municipalities and avoid boom and bust cycles by promoting initiatives seeking sustainable economic growth and economic diversification at the local level in Legal Amazonia. In the complete paper, we will explore in some detail the major implications of this contextual assessment for public policies in Legal Amazonia.